

A butterfly effect in subarachnoid hemorrhage: Autograft healing and renal vulnerability after decompressive craniectomy

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Abstract

Subarachnoid hemorrhage (SAH) is a neurological disease that has a complex pathogenesis resulting from blood flow into the subarachnoid space. It is associated with a high rate of morbidity and mortality and is caused due to traumatic and non-traumatic factors. Although SAH primarily affects brain tissue and leads to neurological symptoms, it is increasingly recognized that distant organs may also be involved. Among these non-neurological complications, Acute Kidney Injury (AKI) stands out as a frequent and clinically significant event. In cases of refractory intracranial hypertension, Decompressive Craniectomy (DC) is a surgical method often performed to diminish intracranial pressure. However, this surgical intervention imposes a secondary systemic burden that may heighten renal vulnerability due to the subsequent physiological demands of autograft preservation and healing. Based on this framework, the present review summarizes the pathophysiological mechanisms connecting SAH, autograft healing, and AKI. Available evidence suggests that AKI is not only a result of a serious condition but also a relevant factor influencing disease progression and prognosis. Moreover, this review highlights key clinical risk factors and discusses the prognostic implications of renal dysfunction in patients with SAH.

Keywords: *Subarachnoid hemorrhage, acute renal injury, kidney failure, complications, autograft healing, decompressive craniectomy*

1. Subarachnoid Hemorrhage Definition and Clinical Presentation

Subarachnoid hemorrhage (SAH) is a neurological problem resulting from bleeding into the subarachnoid space.¹ It is reported that over 30,000 people suffer every year, and approximately 27% of post-SAH people die under the age of 65. The mortality rates are diminished due to new therapeutic endeavors, reduction of hypertension, and non-smoking approaches. Although the descendence, it is still identified as a devastating disease that leads to morbidity or mortality.^{2,3}

SAH originates from a traumatic or non-traumatic situation that results in blood flow. Although genetic factors are important, hypertension, smoking, alcoholism, and drug abuse, which are changeable risk factors, are essential causes of SAH, resulting in comparatively early age of initiation and poor prognosis (Figure 1).^{4,5} It usually begins with an increasing headache that feels like the worst pain ever. Followed by either leg buckling or a brief loss of consciousness, and then generally vomiting. Depending on the location of the bleeding vessel, focal neurological symptoms could be obtainable. On the other hand, it is reported that SAH does not show any symptoms, so it could be challenging to make the proper diagnosis at the right time.⁶

2. Pathophysiology of Subarachnoid Hemorrhage

SAH occurs from traumatic and non-traumatic reasons.

Although trauma seems to be the most common cause of SAH, its importance is sometimes overlooked by the impact of other concurrent traumatic brain injuries. Three main different vascular pathologies that depend on non-traumatic factors: (1) Cerebral artery saccular aneurysm rupture, (2) Arteriovenous malformation, and (3) Idiopathic.⁷ Among them, rupture of saccular aneurysms is the most common, which occurs in approximately 80%.

Following the rupture of the vessel that allows blood to enter the subarachnoid space, cerebrospinal fluid and blood mix. Results of the flow: arterial spasm desendances, but it causes ischemia and infarction in the cerebrum. Although the clotting occurs in the vessel, the Effects of the pathological process continue and are divided into two phases. The first phase, which identifies early brain injury, occurs within the first 72 hours after SAH. The second phase, known as delayed cerebral ischemia, begins 72 hours after the initial ischemic event and continues for 14 days.^{7,8}

After SAH, several pathophysiological alterations cause early hemodynamic disturbances and cellular and molecular injury mechanisms. Following SAH, increased intracranial pressure reduces cerebral perfusion pressure, leading to regional changes in cerebral blood flow. This hemodynamic impairment damages endothelial cells and the blood-brain barrier. Due to these reasons, cerebral edema has occurred. Moreover, a vicious circle is

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Figure 1. Pathophysiological pathways lead to SAH.

triggered between cerebral edema and global cerebral ischemia.

On the other hand, erythrocytes and platelets in leaky blood inside the subarachnoid space accumulate in the area. The group of cells initiates the coagulation cascade and increases the release of pro-inflammatory cytokines, including tumor necrosis factor- α (TNF- α), interleukin-1 β (IL-1 β), and interleukin-6 (IL-6), through inflammatory pathways. In another way, blood extravasation into the subarachnoid space causes an ionic imbalance, triggering both oxidative stress and inflammatory responses. Thus, neuronal death and neuroinflammation are reduced. In parallel, reducing cranial pressure can lead to vascular compression, vasospasm, and occlusion. It results in global cerebral ischemia and focal tissue hypoxia accompanied by increased vascular heterogeneity and the establishment of a prothrombotic microenvironment. All these mechanisms that cause to happen focal hypoxia with oxidative injury, excessive reactive oxygen species production, excitatory amino acid release, activation of the apoptotic pathway, and progressive blood-brain barrier disruption, lead to neuronal energy failure and sustain neuronal dysfunction. Collectively, these interconnected processes constitute the fundamental mechanisms underlying poor neurological outcomes following SAH.^{4,8}

3. Complications of Subarachnoid Hemorrhage

SAH, although accounting for only approximately 5% of all stroke cases, remains a highly devastating condition, with mortality rates approaching 50% and fewer than half of survivors achieving functional independence. SAH itself is associated with substantial morbidity and mortality, and the development of additional complications further increases the complexity of patient management. The neurocritical care course of patients with SAH is frequently complicated.^{9,10}

In recent years, it has been shown that not only neurological but also non-neurological extracerebral complications are essential for progression (Figure 2). Following SAH, pulmonary edema and pneumonia, cardiac arrhythmia, renal and hepatic dysfunction, electrolyte imbalance, and hematologic disorders are the most common non-neurologic medical consequences. Non-neurologic complications following SAH are commonly seen because patients are exceedingly vulnerable. These complications could be observed with brain injury after SAH, resulting in worsening progression at the acute stage.¹¹

4. Acute Kidney Injury as a Complication of Subarachnoid Hemorrhage

Figure 2. The systems are affected by SAH.

Acute kidney injury (AKI) is a sudden reduction in renal function detected by elevated serum creatinine levels and decreased urine output.¹² AKI can be divided into three types based on its pathophysiological mechanisms and the affected anatomic area of injury: pre-renal, intrinsic renal, and post-renal. When etiological subtypes of AKI are considered, they can be categorized into AKI induced by ischemia, infection, sepsis, contrast, and drug. Because AKI types vary, they have different etiologies.¹³

AKI represents a frequent yet often underrecognized extracerebral complication following SAH, with reported incidence rates ranging between 1% and 7% depending on patient characteristics and disease severity.⁹ Clinical studies consistently demonstrate that the development of AKI after SAH is multifactorial, with advanced age, pre-existing renal dysfunction, high hemorrhage burden as reflected by Hunt–Hess grading, intraventricular hemorrhage, and delayed cerebral ischemia emerging as major contributors.^{9,11,14} Moreover, it is clearly indicated that patients with acute SAH are more vulnerable to secondary systemic insults, including sepsis, electrolyte disturbances, and multiorgan dysfunction.^{10,11} The situation investigates pathophysiological aspects, sympathetic activation by catecholamine release causes systemic vasoconstriction, inflammatory activation, and endothelial dysfunction after SAH, which has a role affecting the disorder of renal perfusion and microcirculatory integrity.¹¹ In addition, repeated exposure to contrast agents and aggressive fluid and electrolyte management strategies commonly employed in SAH patients may further predispose them to renal injury.¹⁵ Furthermore, it is determined that even if AKI does not exist, mild impairments in renal function have been shown to independently predict poor short-term neurological outcomes and increased mortality following SAH.¹⁴ Collectively, these findings indicate that AKI constitutes a clinically relevant determinant of prognosis rather than

a secondary bystander event in the course of SAH. It is reported that a minor reduction of kidney function leads to a poor prognosis for the next 3 months in the SAH.¹⁴ In another study that includes 1267 SAH patients, it is reported that the mortality rate is significantly increased in patients with AKI.¹⁵

5. Vulnerability to Acute Kidney Injury Following Decompressive Craniectomy in Subarachnoid Hemorrhage

Decompressive Craniotomy (DC) is an ultimate treatment option used for arresting intracranial pressure, so SAH is an indicator of the usefulness of this technique.¹⁶ The standard neurosurgical approach for intractable intracranial hypertension involves an autologous bone graft that preserves cryopreservation or subcutaneous implantation to the anterior abdominal wall area.¹⁷ Following the autograft healing process occurs in the body. According to a study, a systematic review and meta-analysis, DC is indicated that approximately one in ten aneurysmal SAH patients require DC.¹⁶ Another study revealed that DC is critical for SAH patients' functional recovery as well as mortality.¹⁸

Indeed, DC consists of an autograft healing process that could be compelling to the body due to its sequential process involving inflammation, revascularization, osteogenesis, and remodeling.¹⁹ SAH patients are exceedingly vulnerable, as mentioned above, so it could be readily accepted that the autograft healing process after SAH may make individuals more susceptible to potential complications. Also, a study consisting of 50,691 patients who underwent a craniotomy showed that emergent craniotomy is a risk factor for AKI.²⁰ In this vulnerable clinical setting, surgical stress and the metabolic demands of graft healing may increase the risk of kidney injury, especially in patients with pre-existing risk factors. However, direct mechanistic evidence for this

association is still limited.

6. Conclusion and Future Perspective

Acute kidney injury (AKI) has a substantial impact on survival and functional recovery in patients with subarachnoid hemorrhage (SAH). Although renal dysfunction may initially appear to be a manageable or secondary complication, clinical evidence indicates that it plays a key role in determining prognosis through the combined effects of sympathetic activation, systemic inflammation, and the metabolic demands of neurocritical care. After DC, even localized processes such as autologous bone graft healing become additional sources of inflammatory and metabolic stress. The situation could increase susceptibility to AKI in an already vulnerable patient with SAH. Thereby, relatively small physiological disturbances may lead to disproportionate systemic consequences, a phenomenon that can be conceptually described as a butterfly effect within the brain–kidney axis.

To diminish mortality and morbidity in SAH, several adjunctive strategies may help reduce and prevent vulnerability. According to experimental and clinical studies, agents including melatonin can assist in the recovery of critically fragile patients and have protective effects on a number of organs, including the brain, kidney, and bone. Furthermore, SAH care needs to include minimizing inappropriate contrast exposure and avoiding excessive fluid intake. Also, for determining early renal condition during the acute phase, biomarkers aside from serum creatinine should be identified and validated. Renal monitoring could be prevented by reframing it as an active part of SAH therapy rather than a secondary consideration. Ultimately, survivors' outcomes and quality of life may be enhanced by the protective approaches integrated into clinics.

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Ethical approval

This study does not require approval from the Ethics Committee for Animal Experiments.

Authors contribution

CA: Research, planning, article scanning, writing original draft & review.

Conflict of interest

There are no conflicts of interest associated with this research publication, according to the authors.

Data availability

The data that support the findings of this study are available from the corresponding author upon reasonable request.

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